

Randomized, Controlled Trial of an Educational Intervention to Promote Spectacle Use among Secondary School Children in Islamabad, Pakistan

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Abstract

Uncorrected refractive errors among school age children can adversely affect the school performance and quality of life. Provision of spectacles is the simple solution to correct refractive errors and improve school performance. Unfortunately, adherence to spectacle wear is a big issue among school age children. Lack of understanding about benefits of spectacles wear is the main reason for non-adherence. There is a crucial need to increase awareness among children, parents and teachers about importance of spectacle use for academic performance. This study

Objective: To test an educational intervention to promote spectacle wear among secondary school children of Islamabad Pakistan.

Design: Randomized Controlled Trial.

Participants: Children of age group 11- 16 years from public sector secondary schools of Islamabad Pakistan.

Methods: Vision screening of children was done in both intervention and control arms by a trained optometrist. Autorefraction and subjective refraction of Children with visual acuity $\leq 6/12$ was performed and prescription of spectacles was given. At 3 months follow up purchase and use of spectacles was assessed and at 6 months follow up compliance to spectacle wear was observed before intervention. After 6 months follow up educational intervention was given in intervention arm. At 12 months follow up compliance to spectacle wear was observed after intervention.

Analysis was done on SPSS version 23 and percentage compliance between two arms was compared. Compliance to spectacle wear before and after intervention within intervention arm was also compared. To predict spectacle wear compliance logistic regression was performed.

Main Outcome Measures: Compliance to spectacle wear.

Results: Follow up after intervention shows 47% compliance in control arm while 62% compliance in intervention arm. Mathematically there is 15% difference of spectacle compliance among control and intervention arms and this difference is also statistically significant difference with p - value $0.02 < 0.1$ and OR was calculated as 1.89 with 95% CI as 1.0 – 3.25.

Spectacle compliance before intervention within the intervention arm was recorded as 46% and after intervention in the same group was measured as 62%. There is 16% difference in spectacle compliance before and after intervention in this arm. This difference is statistically significant with p -value $0.00 < 0.1$, OR 3 and 95% CI as 2.16 – 4.16

Logistic regression to predict spectacle wear compliance find out that children in the intervention arm were 2 times more compliant to spectacle wear as compared to children in control arm.

Conclusion: A comprehensive educational intervention to educate teachers, parents and children about the importance of wearing spectacles has the potential to increase spectacle wear among secondary school children.

Introduction

Uncorrected refractive errors are the major cause of avoidable visual impairment. Therefore, these are considered as a public health issue. Uncorrected refractive errors in school aged children can have adverse effects on school performance, academic performance and social activities.¹ A study reported that visual impairment can cause daily life impairment, visual impairment related to refractive errors can be treated by spectacle use and improves daily life.² Same findings were obtained by another study that children with good compliance to spectacle use shows better academic records when compared with those having less compliance

to spectacle use.³ Another study from Los Angeles concluded that by correcting refractive errors children's psychosocial wellbeing and academic performance can be improved.⁴

Problem of uncorrected refractive error have been addressed by number of programs initiated by The World Health Organization. These programs involve school-based vision screening and provision of glasses. The success of these school eye screening programs depends on compliance to spectacle wear. Unfortunately, the follow ups of these programs show that children who were advised and provided with spectacles were not wearing spectacles.^{5,6} Even free provision of glasses cannot increase compliance to spectacle use $\leq 20\%$ compliance rate was observed in a study with free provision of glasses.⁷ Same findings were shown by a study conducted in Tanzania which shows that compliance to free provision of glasses was less when compared with compliance to purchased glasses.⁸

It is obvious that if provision of free glasses cannot increase compliance rate than definitely there are some other factors which are responsible for low compliance rate. A study conducted in India find out that education of Father was strongly associated with compliance rate.³ A study from Saudi Arabia regarding spectacle compliance reported that main reason for non-compliance was parents disapprove. This study also finds out that compliance is comparatively more in adult population than school aged children.⁹ whereas a study conducted on school aged Mexican children finds out that older and urban children are less likely to wear spectacle as compared to rural children.⁷

Adherence to spectacle wear is a big challenge studies find out number of barriers towards spectacle use in school age children. Findings of different studies shows that reasons for not using glasses differ with population, commonly founded reasons were broken or lost spectacles, eye glasses at home, concerned about appearance, parental disapproval, use only for special occasions, teased by peers and belief of weakening of eyes by using spectacles.^{10,11,8} A qualitative study from South India reported many psychological and social barriers including some sensitive one like naming and teasing by others.¹² A study on school age children from Pakistan reported that 28% students don't like to wear spectacle and 19% were not using due to peer pressure whereas 15 % were facing financial issues these results indicate that psychosocial reasons for non-compliance to spectacle wear were more than financial issue.¹³ Similar findings were reported by another study from Pakistan which concluded that major reason for non-compliance to spectacle wear was don't like to wear that is a psychosocial issue.¹⁴

Lack of awareness about importance of spectacle use for learning process was found as the major reason for noncompliance. A study on perceptions about refractive errors from Pakistan concluded that lack of awareness and cultural factors are the main reasons for not wearing spectacles.¹⁵ A qualitative study conducted focus group discussions with teachers and parents in China reported that lack of awareness about the benefits of spectacle use was the major barrier towards spectacle use rather than the cost of spectacles. They also concluded after assessing attitudes of students, teachers and parents that knowledge gap about importance of spectacle use during learning process should be addressed through educational programs.¹⁶ similar findings were also reported by other studies.^{14,17} Therefore, the present study planned an educational intervention to raise awareness about benefits of spectacle use during learning process. Participants of this educational intervention were children with refractive errors, their parents and teachers. To encourage the students to use spectacle it is needed to provide awareness about benefits of spectacle use to children, parents and teachers. A study conducted in rural China used educational intervention to promote purchase of spectacles among school age children unfortunately that intervention failed to increase purchase of spectacles.¹⁸ Another study from India to evaluate effectiveness of an interventional package to promote compliance to spectacle use concluded that interventional package was effective to increase spectacle compliance.¹⁹

There is a crucial need to decrease the prevalence of avoidable visual impairment related to uncorrected refractive errors. Present study was planned to create awareness among children, teachers and parents regarding importance of spectacle use to increase compliance towards spectacles use. This could be a step towards reducing avoidable visual impairment due to uncorrected refractive errors. This is the first interventional study to promote compliance towards spectacle use in Pakistan.

Participants and Method:

Study design:

A single blind, randomized controlled trial of an educational intervention to promote spectacle wear among secondary school children was done in Islamabad, Pakistan. Islamabad is the capital city of Pakistan with highest literacy rate as 88 %. Cost of living in Islamabad is also highest and population is mostly upper middle class and middle class with unemployment rate as 15.70%.

Procedure:

After approval of study protocol by the Ethical committee of ISRA University Islamabad Campus a permission letter from Federal Directorate of Education Islamabad (FDE) was obtained. A list of public sector secondary schools was obtained from FDE. Schools were stratified by gender four schools from each stratum were selected by simple random sampling. Each school in the strata had equal opportunity to participate in the trial. Due to limited time and resources only 8 schools were selected to participate in the trial.

Selected schools were visited by principle investigator to provide information sheet and permission letter from FDE to the principals of schools. Written and informed consent for vision screening of children was obtained from the principals. An information sheet in local language was sent to the parents of children selected for vision screening. It was explained that vision of their child will assessed and prescription of glasses will be given if needed. They were allowed to refuse if they don't want vision screening of their child. Information sheet was given to participants of focus group discussions and written consent was obtained from each participant. Children and parents selected to participate in the focus group discussion were given information sheet and consent form in local language. Information sheet and consent forms were read out loud in case parents were not able to read.

Participants:

Children from 6th to 9th grade (approximate age, 11-16 years) of secondary schools in Islamabad, Pakistan.

Sample Size Calculation:

Calculated sample size was based on the results of previous study conducted in Rawalpindi that reported 41% spectacle compliance. Considering two-sided significance level as 1-alpha, power of 80 % and one is to one ratio between intervention and control groups, the sample size for each group was calculated as 106. Considering 10% non-response rate and rounding up it was estimated that each group would need 120 children with refractive error. To overcome the ethical issues after final collection of data at 12 months follow up, schools in the control arm were given same intervention to promote spectacle wear.

Randomization:

Stratified random sampling technique was used to assign schools to receive an educational intervention and schools to serve as controls. Four schools (2 boys and 2girls) were selected for intervention arm and four schools (2boys and 2girls) were selected for Control arm. Eligible schools had equal chance to be selected for trial.

Participant Recruitment:

In order to recruit estimated sample size of 120 children with refractive errors for each arm vision screening of 6th, 7th, 8th and 9th grade students in each school was performed. One section from each 6th to 9th grade classes was selected by simple random sampling technique. In each arm of the study 60 girls and 60 boys with refractive error were recruited.

Inclusion Criteria: Students with refractive errors and age group 11-16 years were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria: student in 10th grade were excluded from the study as this interventional study was about one year long and on follow ups 10th grade might not be available in the schools. Students having eye disorders other than refractive error were also excluded.

Study Flow Chart:

Autorefractometer was used for students with VA ≤ 6/12 at least in one eye that could be improved with pinhole. Refractive Errors such as Myopia, Hypermetropia and Astigmatism were defined as spherical equivalent (S.E) of ≥-0.5 D, ≥+ 1.0 D and ≥ 0.75 D, respectively.

Data about age, gender, visual acuity, type of refractive error, mother's and father's education level, spectacles given before, use of given spectacles was collected from all the students with refractive error. At auto refraction desk optometrist collected above information by using a structured questionnaire. After autorefraction, subjective refraction was done by professional optometrist and prescription of glasses was given to students.

Table:1 Characteristics of Children Recommended to Obtain Spectacles in both arms.

Characteristic	Intervention Arm	Control Arm
Mean age in years (SD)	13.49 (1.56)	13.61 (1.49)
Girls (%)	60 (50%)	60 (50%)
Median uncorrected VA in better eye	6/12	6/12
Median best corrected VA in better eye	6/6	6/6
Mean spherical equivalent refractive error in better eye	1.62 (.90)	1.66 (1.30)
Owned spectacles at baseline (%)	58.33%	55.83%

SD = Standard deviation, VA = Visual Acuity

Educational Intervention:

Focus group discussions (FGDs) with non-compliant children, their teachers and parents were done to explore barriers towards spectacle wear and suggestions to overcome these barriers. Considering these barriers and suggestions an educational intervention was planned for children, teachers and parents. This educational intervention was combined with conduct of screening, refraction by trained optometrist and provision of accurate prescription. Intervention was given at 6 months after prescribing glasses at baseline assessment. Intervention was given in two girls schools and two boys schools included in the intervention arm. Details of given intervention are as following:

- Lecture on importance of spectacles use by an optometrist was delivered on multimedia and included visual materials such as pictures and videos. Children, teachers and parents attended the session.
- A classroom-based demonstration was carried out by trained optometrist. Children with refractive error were asked to read 6/6 vision level on Snellen chart from 6 meters distance without glasses and then with glasses. The purpose of this demonstration was to show them Impact of glasses wear on their vision.
- Posters at gate, inside school and in Lecture halls were pasted
- Brochures were distributed to children, teachers and parents.

Evidence before this study: Same educational intervention was used in See Well to Learn Well study in China, unfortunately they couldn't find increase in compliance after intervention.

Added Value of this study: Previous study only focuses on children and intervention didn't include posters and brochures. Present study involve children their classmates, teachers and parents as well. This study includes posters and brochures along with classroom demonstration and lectures.

Follow ups and Outcome Assessments:

After baseline assessment these children were visited at 3 months follow up, 6 months follow up and 12 months follow up. A person who was not aware of intervention and control arm was trained to observe compliance to spectacle wear on follow ups.

At three months follow up purchase and use of spectacle was observed and was recorded as compliance to spectacle wear. At 6 months follow up compliance to spectacle wear was observed before intervention. After six-month intervention was given in four schools included in intervention arm. At 12 months follow up spectacle compliance was observed after intervention. Before intervention follow up was at 6 months after prescription of glasses given at baseline. After intervention follow up was at 6 months after intervention was given to the children their parents and teachers. At follow ups main outcome measure was compliance to spectacle use.

Masking: Person responsible to assess outcome was masked about allocation of intervention and control arms.

Loss to follow up:

In the control arm 6% children were not available at 3 months follow up while in the intervention arm 7% were not available. Loss to follow up at 6 month was 7% in control arm while it was 10% in the intervention arm. At 12 months loss to follow up in the control group was 9% where as in the intervention arm it was 8%. Children available for follow up at these three time periods are shown in the Table 2.

Table:2. Number of children available for follow ups at the three time periods

Arms	3 months follow up	6 months follow ups	12 month follow up
Control (120 children enrolled)	113(94%)	112 (93%)	109 (91%)

Intervention (120 children enrolled)	111 (93%)	108 (90%)	110 (92%)
Total (240)	224 (93%)	220 (92%)	219 (91%)

Table.2 shows loss to follow up increases with time period this may be due to the absentees from school or some children leave the school. Difference in the number of children available for follow ups at three time periods between the two arms is not a big difference.

Data Analysis:

All statistical analysis was performed with the help of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23. Difference in the proportion of compliance between the control and intervention arm was calculated with the chi-squared test of association and odds ratios were calculated to measure the association. Logistic regression was performed to understand the effect of intervention on compliance adjusting for other factors like age and unaided visual acuity. All data analysis was performed using the 0.1 α -level to assess statistical significance.

Results:

This study recruited 240 children with refractive error who required spectacle correction among 1430 children. 120 children with refractive error were recruited from control arm which included four schools (2 boys and 2 girls). Similarly, 120 children who require spectacle correction were recruited from intervention arm that also include (2 boys and 2 girls) schools. A professional optometrist provides prescription of glasses to the children with refractive errors after subjective refraction according to the autorefraction findings.

Comparison of Refractive Errors among Control and Intervention Arms:

Prevalence of refractive errors in each group can be compared on the basis of their frequencies. Myopic refractive error was found in 27% of children of intervention arm and 29% children of control arm. Prevalence of hypermetropia was found 10% in intervention arm and 9% in control arm. Myopic Astigmatism was found in 8% children among intervention arm and 10% in control arm. These refractive error frequencies are presented in the table 3.

Table:3 Frequency of refractive errors among control and intervention arms.

	Frequency of Refractive Errors				Total
	Myopia No (% age)	Hypermetropia No (% age)	Myopic Astigmatism No (% age)	Hypermetropic Astigmatism No (% age)	
Intervention Arm	66 (27%)	25 (10%)	19 (8%)	10 (4 %)	120 (50%)
Control Arm	69 (29%)	21 (9 %)	24 (10 %)	6 (3 %)	120 (50%)
Total	135 (56%)	46 (19%)	43 (18%)	16 (7%)	240 (100%)

Comparison of Spectacle Compliance between Control and Intervention Arms:

Comparison of Compliance to spectacle wear among control and intervention arm at different time period is given in the table.4. Significance level, OR and 95% CI are also calculated with chi square test to see statistically significant difference of spectacle compliance among two arms. Compliance rate at six months follow up was considered as compliance before intervention and compliance rate at 12 months follow up was considered as compliance after intervention. Follow up 6 months after prescribing glasses shows 50% compliance in control arm while 46% in intervention arm. The difference in compliance to spectacle use between the two arms at this follow ups was not statistically significant with p value more than 0.1 as calculated by chi-square test $X^2(df = 1, N = 220) = 0.302, p = 0.58$

At 12 months follow up the intervention arm shows statistically significant higher compliance than control arm with OR as 1.89 and 95% CI as 1.1– 3.25 p-value less than 0.1 as calculated by chi-square test $X^2(df = 1, N = 220) = 5.62, p = 0.02$

Table:4. Spectacle compliance in the control and intervention arms at different time period.

Compliance at Follow-ups	Control group	Intervention group	Significance level p-value	Odds Ratio	95% confidence interval

6 months follow up (Before Intervention)	50%	46%	0.583	0.862	0.508-1.464
12 months follow up (After Intervention)	47%	63%	0.018	1.914	1.116 - 3.282

Figure 1 shows that before educational intervention there is no significant difference in spectacle compliance between controls and intervention arms. Whereas after intervention the difference in spectacles compliance between control and intervention arms is observable. Mathematically there is 15% difference of spectacle compliance among control and intervention arms and this difference is also statistically significant.

Fig:1. Comparison of Percentage compliance to spectacle wears in both arms at follow-ups.

Comparison of compliance before and after intervention with in intervention arm

Spectacle compliance before intervention was measured at 6 month follow up and was recorded as 46% in intervention arm. Compliance to spectacle wear six months after intervention in the same group was measured as 62%. This difference in spectacles compliance before and after intervention with in intervention arm is shown in fig 2.

Fig: 2 Comparison of compliance before and after intervention with in intervention arm.

There is 16% difference in spectacle compliance before and after intervention in this group. This difference is statistically significant with p-value $0.00 < 0.1$, OR 3 and 95% CI as 2.16 – 4.16.

Logistic regression was performed to find out the effect of intervention on compliance adjusting for other factors like age and unaided visual acuity. Analysis determine that intervention would predict compliance to spectacle wear having Odds Ratio 2.1 with 95% CI as 1.16- 3.91 and p- value $0.01 < 0.1$. This result can be interpreted as “children in the intervention arm are 2 times more compliant to spectacle wear as compared to the children in control arm”

Discussion:

Present study planned an educational intervention to promote spectacles use among secondary school children. Intervention was planned to raise awareness about benefits of spectacle use during learning process among children, teachers and parents. This educational intervention was planned to overcome barriers to spectacle wear explored through focus group discussions with children, their parents and teachers. Participants of this educational intervention were children with refractive errors, their classmates, their parents and teachers. Results of present study shows that comprehensive educational intervention given to children, parents and teachers can improve compliance towards spectacle use among secondary school children. Similar study with educational intervention was conducted in China¹⁸ focusing on children only who received a lecture, video and demonstration to show improvement of visual acuity with spectacle in the class room setting and explain benefits of spectacle use to them. That intervention was not found successful and could not improve compliance towards spectacle use, whereas present study involves children, their classmates, their parents and teachers in the educational intervention. During intervention lectures were delivered on multimedia, demonstration was given to show improvement in visual acuity with spectacles wear, posters were pasted at the prominent places in the school and brochures were distributed among all participants.

Present intervention was found successful as follow up after intervention shows statistically significant increase in compliance rate among intervention arm. Similar results were shown by another study conducted in India that concluded effectiveness of an educational intervention in promoting compliance to spectacle wear. That study involves combined intervention that includes conduct of screening, frame related guidance, awareness and encouragement to use spectacle through education.¹⁹

Present study found 15% increase in compliance rate after a comprehensive educational intervention by professional optometrist while another study report increased compliance by 81.5% after combined intervention which include education, free provision of glasses and incentive to teachers.²⁰ Another study shows 47% increase in compliance with three pack intervention including optometric screening, teacher's encouragement and free provision of glasses.⁶ While a school-based intervention to provide two pairs of free spectacles was not found successful and couldn't increase compliance to spectacle wear.²¹ This is obvious from result of these studies that provision of free spectacle alone couldn't improve compliance to spectacle wear, whereas free provision of glasses in combination with education and incentives has potential to improve spectacles compliance.

Results of present study shows that children in intervention arm are 2 times more compliant to spectacle wear as compare to control arm. Whereas study from India that involve combined intervention reported that children in intervention arm are 4 times more compliant than children in control arm.¹⁹

Findings from previous studies show that combined interventions are more successful than single intervention as combinations can overcome many barriers. Although the present study provides only educational intervention but this intervention was provided by professional optometrists and was comprehensive including lectures, demonstration, posters and brochures distributions. Intervention was planned after exploring all the potential barriers to spectacle wear through focus group discussions with children, their teachers and parents. Present study creates awareness about importance of spectacle use among parents, teachers and classmates of the children with refractive errors. As coordination between teachers and parents is necessary to understand the need of spectacles use for children, present study provides opportunity for this coordination between teachers and parents. This is the first educational intervention study to promote spectacle wear among secondary school children in Pakistan.

Weakness: Due to lack of time and resources only 8 schools were enrolled for trial. This study couldn't provide free glasses and only prescription for glasses was given.

Strengths: To overcome the risk of wrong prescriptions this study provides accurate prescriptions of glasses by professional optometrist through subjective refraction according to autorefraction findings. Educational intervention was planned by considering potential barriers to spectacle wear which were explored by focus group discussions with children, their parents and teachers. This study creates awareness about importance of spectacle wear among the children with refractive errors their parents and teachers.

Conclusion:

Compliance to spectacle wear among secondary school children was measured significantly low at base line data collection. While exploring barriers towards spectacle wear it was found that lack of awareness and knowledge about benefits of spectacle wear leads to many psychological and social barriers that affects compliance towards spectacle wear. There was a crucial need to plan an educational intervention to improve compliance to spectacle wear that could ultimately increase school performance. Therefore, present study planned an educational intervention to generate awareness about importance of spectacle use among children with refractive errors, their parents and teachers. It was concluded that a comprehensive educational intervention involving children, parents and teachers can improve compliance towards spectacle use among secondary school children.

Recommendations:

1. Spectacle compliance could be increased significantly if need and benefits of spectacle wear are explained to children and their parents at the time of prescription.
2. School and teachers can also play an important role to increase spectacle wear by counseling children and their parents about importance of spectacle wear for learning process.
3. There should be a close coordination between parents and teachers about spectacle wear.
4. Educational interventions are needed to increase awareness about importance of spectacle wear for learning process.

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